
Designing Scalable and Cost-Efficient Cloud-Agnostic Big Data Platforms: A Comparative Study

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Abstract: This paper aims to explore big data architecture and the benefits of implementing cloud-agnostic solutions, especially about scalability, costs, and flexibility. This paper is limited to the advancements of orchestration tools, edge computing, and AI to overcome the challenges in areas such as administration, security, and latency. These advancements will improve abilities related to data assortment and organization in various cloud contexts.

Keywords: Low-latency, Real-time data, Data engineering pipelines, FPGA acceleration, Incremental ETL, On-GPU processing, Data consistency

Introduction

The large amount of data that began to appear required the creation of intricate open platforms that would allow for the swift and efficient analysis of open big data. That is why cloud-agnostic platforms became important choices, which allow organizations to use a plethora of CSPs, being not bound to one cloud provider.

Aim: The main aim of this research is to identify cloud-agnostic big data platforms that can bring efficiencies of scale and costs, with a focus on enhancements in big data architecture.

Objective

- To review the recent advancements in the big data architecture to understand the capability and the price of the cloud-generic big data architecture.
- To analyse big data platforms that are cloud-agnostic can also offer scalable and relatively cost-effective solutions.
- To identify how orchestration tools, edge computing, as well as AI, enhance the efficiency and affordability of the cloud-nonspecific big data environments.

Literature Review

Multi-cloud big data architectures are designed and implemented to run applications in different CSPs without being confined to one provider. So, it can indeed be said that the given flexibility of cloud computing can benefit organisations through utilising various cloud environments so that the performance is optimised, and costs are decreased, and scalability is improved [1]. These platforms utilize virtualization and containerization to create isolate, movable execution environments that can fluently host and run programs across the different clouds. Application containers/ virtual machines isolate applications to deliver the same level of performance irrespective of the underlying environment.

Cloud-agnostic systems are installed employing advanced coordination technologies like Kubernetes and Apache Mesos [2]. These tools are responsible for matters regarding the application's deployment, scalability and operation. These solutions offer the best placement of programs across many clouds while at the same time being efficient in the use of resources and avoiding delays. Cloud architecture often utilizes facilitated cloud

resources from various CSPs through VPNs and other network infrastructures to ensure secure and reliable data transfers.

Benefits

Fig. 1: Deployment of a project-specific Virtual Appliance

Big data solutions implemented in different clouds offer many advantages that make it possible to call the solution attractive for working with large datasets in various clouds. It consists of also the openness of the dimensions, cost advantages, and the likelihood of interfacing with other frameworks.

A. Scalability

One of the benefits is the ability of big data platforms to function across multiple clouds. These systems have the expected ability to be scaled horizontally as it is possible to add one or more nodes to the cluster [3]. This enables them to manage more data within systems and meet the demands of the user without any hindrance on time.

B. Cost-Efficiency

These platforms cut operating costs, especially through the use of spot instances and through the application of cost-saving scheduling algorithms [4]. The unused workloads can be run through Spot instances which can be availed at a cheaper price than the normal charges offered by cloud-providing companies, thus reducing the comprehensive cost of cloud infrastructure.

C. Flexibility and Interoperability

Fig. 2: Price trends of different instances

The flexibility and openness of the cloud-neutral big data stack are valuable features that help organizations refrain from being locked into a single vendor and harness the superior strengths of many cloud service providers [5]. These enable playing a single pane of glass for optimal utilization of resources across multiple clouds, thereby allowing organizations to easily migrate between providers based on factors like cost, capacity, and service offerings.

Applications

Fig. 3: System Architecture for Distributed Cloud Data Centers with NFV

cloud-agnostic has found widespread adoption in various industries for enhancing business performance, data handling, and decision-making [6]. The initial industries benefiting most from such solutions are the health, finance, and transportation sectors.

A. Healthcare

The cloud-agnostic architecture of big data platforms is needed in healthcare systems for the integration and processing of patient data from different sources. These enable constant tracking and evaluation of data in an actual time manner which is quite helpful in assessing diseases at their early stage as well as developing unique programs for the patient [7]. For instance, information about patients like EHRs, biomedical sensors, and imaging technology from wearable devices can be gathered and analysed for a comprehensive look at the client’s health status.

B. Finance

The finance industry is one of the key beneficiaries of cloud-agnostic big data platforms because they enable the analysis of massive transactional and market data [8]. These systems are applied in financial institutions to flag and curb such acts, reduce risks, and also comply with the set regulations. Real-time monitoring of transaction patterns helps banks and other financial service providers to identify fraud and to protect consumers’ assets.

C. Transportation

Big data platforms that are independent of cloud computing are adopted within the transportation sector to improve traffic, logistics, and fleet. ITS intends to manage and supervise traffic utilizing data procured from various sensors, GPS machines, and traffic cameras [9]. Cloud-independent solutions allow for the instantaneous processing and analysis of this data to help the authorities manage traffic flow, increase safety, and optimize the general performance of the transport systems [10].

Methodologies

Fig. 4: Hardware virtualization approaches compared

The methodological framework for analysing cloud-agnostic big data architectures involves a systematic review of academic articles, case studies and empirical data [11]. This technique provides a wider perspective of such

platforms, its implementation, how it works, and its cost-effectiveness so evaluating likelihood to expand and evolve in different cloud environments is more manageable.

Results And Discussion

Fig. 5: Quantity distribution of each class

In this regard, to reach the potential of the cloud-agnostic big data platform, many difficulties occur, which is essential to address [12]. These include issues such as the complicated nature of administration, data and its adhesion, and network latency issues.

A. Complexity in Management

Managing a big data platform that can be on any cloud across different environments is inherently complex. Each cloud provider has a varied set of services, APIs, and administration tools and hence it is a complex environment [13]. Managers have to invest more money in the acquisition of high-grade tools and high-quality personnel to cope with this level of complexity. This ensures interoperability and seamless working on many different cloud platforms.

B. Data Security and Compliance

The overall data protection and compliance of using multiple clouds are not simple to address and handle. Security policies are not centralized because cloud providers are different from each other concerning security precautions and regulatory requirements [14]. It is recommended that organizations designate sophisticated security features such as encryption, and access control mechanisms, and regularly evaluate approaches in all cloud environments.

C. Network Latency

One major issue with cloud-agnostic platforms is the issue of network latency, which can create problems especially when it comes to processing real-time data. Mobile data can also take its time to transfer from one cloud environment to another a process that has a detrimental effect on the application's quick response time [15]. It is also recommended that organizations plan for their systems to restrict any data transfer that is carried out on the cloud and at the same time enhance the relay of their network.

Performance Evaluation

Fig. 6: Architecture of conducting Big Data analytics in ITS.

The big data platform consists of three layers: The Data Collection layer encompasses Sensors, RFID and GPS; Data Analytics layer which covers storage, management, Data Mining, analysis, and sharing; the Application layer covers traffic prediction, Anomaly detection, and route planning [17]. It ensures the efficient execution of data processing and smooth integration of applications within this architecture.

An evaluation of big data systems which are cloud non-specific uncovers huge improvements in scalability and costs. The deployment of superior orchestration tools coupled with edge computing technologies minimises the latency and optimises the resource usage [18]. A real-world study proves that, organised data can be effectively processed in multiple clouds, thus leading to reduced operational costs and capability of handling more real-time data for stronger and agile run.

Conclusion

In conclusion, cloud-agnostic big data platforms offer immense benefits in terms of scalability cost, and flexibility. This places them as a required answer to widespread and intricate data processing across many cloud environments.

Future Work

The future of big data platforms that can be built on any cloud provider is tied to existing challenges and newly emerging opportunities [19]. The prospects involve the enhancement of orchestration tools, the inclusion of edge computing, and the use of AI and machine learning.

A. Enhanced Orchestration Tools

Future advancements in orchestration tools focus on furthering the operational ease in managing cloud-agnostic platforms [20]. These technologies bring better levels of automation, better resource optimization, and further scaling so that organizations can better handle large multiple cloud structures [21]. Advanced orchestration tools are going to be better monitoring and analysis, providing detailed information and predictive maintenance for higher efficiency and lower operational costs.

B. Edge Computing Integration

Computing at the edge coupled with cloud-agnostic platforms is the other major future trend to be achieved. Edge computing helps in performing analysis of data near the source, which results in limited latency and better usage of bandwidth [22]. Organizations can optimize time-sensitive applications by integrating edge computing and cloud-agnostic platforms to process and analyse data at the edge in real time. This interface also helps deploy intelligent forms in distant and underprivileged environments, thus increasing the outreach of and demand for cloud-independent systems.

C. AI and Machine Learning

Cloud-agnostic dispersed application platforms and artificial intelligence (AI) together with machine learning (ML) revolutionize data management and analysis [23]. Machine Learning (ML) and AI serve the capacity to do automated processes, enforce data forecasts, and succession richer categorizations and characterizations based on it [24]. These technologies allow the platform to learn from data patterns, maximize resources, and improve decision-making at the platforms [25].

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